

Climate Change : Challenges and Solutions

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Renewable sources of energy exist naturally without depletion since they replenish themselves naturally. Some of the renewable sources of energy include geothermal energy, solar energy, hydropower, bioenergy, wave and tide energy, and wind energy. Unfortunately, the world is experiencing uncontrollable population growth which subsequently leads to continual and excessive consumption of renewable sources of energy. As a result, trade and investment have also developed globally with individuals and states attempting to meet their basic and economic needs. In the long run the excessive use of the energy has resulted to several challenges including depletion of fossil fuels, greenhouse gas emissions and other environmental issues.

Keywords: Renewable Sources, Reforestation, Climate, Environment, Energy, Global Warming, Greenhouse Gases, Carbon IV Oxide, Emission, Industrialization, Paris Agreement, Regional Trade, Depletion, Consumption.

Scientifically, renewable sources of energy are considered as natural and clean sources of energy. However, excessive usage of the energy can lead to adverse effects on the environment and climate. These sources of energy produce acceptable amounts of secondary waste. Therefore, their consumption is sustainable as far as the ongoing and future economic needs are met. Subsequently, industrial use of renewable sources of energy provide good opportunity for mitigating and controlling greenhouse gas emission and reduction in negative climate change attributed to global warming (Ćetković, & Buzogány, 2016). The energy sector contributes to global development through trade. There should be enhanced efforts for enhancing power generation, promotion of regional trade and facilitation of renewable energy. Regional trade can be enhanced by expansion of transmission and distribution of energy networks and interconnection of regional networks. There have been constant efforts associated with strategic investment planning for renewable energy such as introduction of new technologies in electricity generation.

Moreover, with the increasing world's population, countries have stepped up efforts to control global warming and climate change. Protection of the environment has been a key global priority alongside international trade. India is one of the countries that has embraced efforts targeted at encouraging constructive steps towards implementing global climate talks. For instance, a key step in the reduction of domestic emission as a policy has been affected by the Indian government whereby every household and industries are restricted on emission of carbon IV oxide gas. Furthermore, India has joined hands with other countries in declaring a prohibition that industries should not produce temperatures exceeding degrees (Åhman, Nilsson, & Johansson, 2017).

Reforestation is also among the priorities that is currently embraced by the Indian government. It is a step aimed at mitigating global climate change. For instance, the government has set aside 0.8 million hectares of land for forest establishment annually. This effort has been coupled with forest conservation strategies, forest improvement and management. Nevertheless, the Indian government is continuously regenerating and boosting the capacity of local communities by creating job opportunities as a method of minimizing environmental degradation. Indian government has also established missions that constitutes National Action

Plan on Climate Change pushing forward for the expansion and maintenance of Solar Mission and the Mission of Enhanced Energy Efficiency. The solar mission as one of the renewable sources of energy targets about 20 GW of solar generation in the near future. It is among the effective source of energy that is embraced with climate change compliant countries. The mission for enhanced energy efficiency in India starts with initiatives put in place to improve the efficiency of energy consumption across all economy and industrial sectors. To enhance the plan, Indian government has been formulating strategies and policies for mandated standards touching industries, buildings, appliances, vehicles, trade energy consumption and market mechanisms to limit excessive emissions.

Climate change is a major global threat in relation to the growing world's population and industrialization. One of the main causes of climatic change is the carbon emissions into the atmosphere. Moreover, it is caused by greenhouse gas emission, deforestation and land use. All these underlying causes lead to ozone layer depletion hence the rise in temperature and climate change. As a result of carbon emission, the atmosphere is constantly getting polluted. With depletion of the ozone layer to the projection reveals that there is a sudden rise temperature, glaciers are melting resulting to sudden floods (Schandl., et al. 2016). Nevertheless, the atmospheric temperature is rising day by day resulting to global warming (Owusu, & Asumadu-Sarkodie, 2016). By extension Agricultural sector is negatively impacted in attribution to global warming and this has a bigger influence on the international economy. The globe is also experiencing increase in land temperatures as well sea temperatures. Subsequently, there are high risks of coastal erosions and harm to the aquaculture (Rogelj., et al. 2016). Currently, the climate change is also altering the precipitation quantity and patterns leading to unexpected changes in rainfall seasons. Some parts of the globe are experiencing extreme drought and flood attributed to the current climate change. Coastal cities as warned by experts should be on the high alert to face high sea-levels (Gulagi, Bogdanov, & Breyer, 2017). Several studies have also pointed out that carbon emissions and bubbling is more likely to lead to loss of global wealth amounting to 3 trillion dollars. This loss is comparable to the 2007 financial crisis.

Most of the developed countries are shifting their investments to renewable energy from fossil fuels. This effort is implemented through establishment of the appropriate international enabling environment policies. The G 20 for example is committed towards climate proofing of all economies (Kardooni, Yusoff, & Kari, 2016). The international economy is also set to employ compatible strategies in their operations to achieve the Paris Agreement (de Jong., et al. 2017). The countries have also been adopting flexible policies and approaches towards the introduction of renewable energy. This is effective for example, the developing countries lack relevant experience with the introduced policies aimed at transforming their energy sector (Bhan, et al. 2017). There have been capacity building efforts to establish an enabling environment and regulatory policies to initiate introduction of renewable energy. Another effort that has been made by both developing and developed countries is deployment of low-carbon technologies in industrial sectors.

Besides, various technologies have also been introduced that reduce emission of carbon. To achieve the objectives, the governments of these countries allocate finances for research and development. The research is aimed at finding out more about the zero-carbon technology and the current industrial operations (Nowotny., et al. 2018). Most importantly, both developing and developed countries are prohibiting deforestation but adopting sustainable agricultural practices (Larcher, & Tarascon, 2015). Nevertheless, most countries are also enhancing efforts to decrease emissions from agricultural sectors. To achieve healthy and environmental agricultural practices most countries are supporting rural development as well as improving food security.

The ever-expanding world population alongside industrialization are the major threats to climate and global warming. If carbon IV emission is not mitigated, the globe will not be sustainable. It, therefore, calls for a combined effort from both developing and developed countries to adopt renewable energy sources within the vast industrial sector. The population should also be taught on the various environmentally friendly practices to save the world from global warming and greenhouse effect.

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